

BASIC STATEMENT TO DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF UNMANNED SYSTEMS INTO GROUND FORCES UNITS

Zahradnicek Pavel

Dr.

Assistant of professor, University of defence, Brno, Czech republic

ORCID 0000-0002-4307-0936

pavel.zahradnicek@unob.cz

Zezula Jan

Dr.

Chief of department, University of defence, Brno, Czech republic

ORCID 0000-0002-3487-0018

jan.zezula@unob.cz

***Abstract.** The article describes separated attributes, necessary to implement Unmanned ground systems (UGS) as usual part of units and formations. To these attributes, the viewpoint of authors is attached, including references to other studies. The authors' general position is, that UGS's can influence success on battlefield and in longer time period, as a device, will dominate. Bute there exist still couple steps and many technical solutions, before all-domain, all-branches and all types of operations wide utilisation. The aim of article is to boost discussion in community of experts, scientists and scholars. The authors are more focused on ground systems (vehicles), because reaching the autonomy of this kind of device will be sign of start of next generation of warfare. The article is part of NATO Science and technical organisation panel SAS-175 to open discussion for workshop.*

The article consists from 3 main chapters. First chapter shortly describes current state and enable reader to enter the topic. Second chapter explains

technological the tempo of development as a booster and shows on “Kurzweils curve” and necessary reaction. Last chapter set questions and ideas for thinking about this statements and can be also possible ways and inspirations for research.

The view of authors is, that if we (as allies) want implement this technology widely and effectively, we have also to experiment, try to correct the mistakes and fill-in the gaps. And reality is, that amount of experiments seems unsuccessful, because current level of technological advance has some limitations. On the other hand, still to seeing incorrect way is also result, offering new opportunities for decision makers and scientists.

The article is applicable as a part of studies, thesis or starter of discussions or lessons.

Keywords: *Development, implementation, technology, unmanned systems, utilisation.*

1. Current state

UGS participate and participated operational deployment. Especially in high risky missions, for ex. EOD (Explosive ordnance detachment), are UGV’s utilised. Mostly, they are tele-operated and only selected activities they operate semi-automatically. Similar status we can find in cargo UGV (unmanned ground vehicle). In recent operations, they were deployed also combat UGS, equipped by small calibre weapons. Large calibre weapons, grenade launchers, antitank or rocket systems was not noticed in open sources as a deployed entity. But there exists lot of experimental exercises, which can describe current possibilities, strengths and weaknesses of many types of UGV’s.

Conflict in Ukraine shows, that manpower is limited and needs to be also utilised not only for warfare as itself, also for running all the functions of state, in order to avoid system collapse. It means, that combination of technology in all fields and branches, utilising manpower in indispensable actions, keeping basic functions and roles of defence forces will be challenge for next conflict.

Technological development as basic booster

The tempo of technological development is accelerating. Goals, which were set in conceptual documents, are in optimal condition achievable. The milestone will be reaching the capability to sort and prioritise data at all levels [3, p.12-17], including entities as single instruments. According to Kurzweil's curve, this should be reached approx. in next 10 years [2]. This ability will be significant for reaching higher level of autonomy.

Picture 1. The Kurzweil curve [2]

The practical impact for UGS utilisation lies in ability to dispense same level of perception and decision-making by all single devices. In this case we can say, that the machines can substitute human operators. According to authors, this state will be last much longer, because it consists necessarily of miniaturisation, enough manufacture capacities, sustainment system, law system, increasing level of education and training etc.

On the other side, it does not mean, nowadays or in close future, can't cooperate manned-unmanned teams or semi-automated UGS. This option is according to authors more realistic and applicable. From perspective of domain warfare, it consists integration of more domains into warfare on tactical level. The warfare will be going on physical domain (air, land, sea, space) and in information, electronic and cognitive space [4].

2. Utilisation of UxS from perspective of tactical level ground units

UxS add portfolio of instruments for ground commander. They increase amount of instruments for solving almost all types of operations. Reality is, that ground commanders trust on their "best practice". They don't want to experiment in operations, it is too late. What we can do, is introduce capabilities and experiments in "peace time". Focused on ground domain, let's try to implement one small UGV unit into manoeuvre (combat) formation and support them. During lessons identified process react immediately and fix gaps. No delay would be acceptable. Circularly, doing this process again can build the trust. Then, commanders will be willing to want it, not admire it.

We can observe a lot of effort for research and development, across countries. But do we share the experience or know how? Do we cooperate across research? Are we targeting our effort? Don't we make same research and development? Let's optimise it. Offer and share our capabilities and capacities. Otherwise, opposites can disperse these tools quicker and will be more effective than us.

Let's think about implementation into operational unit. The authors are convinced, that we have to start focus on real utilisation. So let's start from bottom up. The smallest entity can be small unit (squad, platoon) equipped by one UGV. There has to be operator working primarily with device, be able to protect himself and be protected by the unit. Because operator with UxS is part of unit, commander has to order them and has to have overview about its activity and overall status. This need advanced forms of commanding solved for ex. by augmented reality. The most

complicated is assignment of combat-UGV's. There is requirement of proper manoeuvre, fire, immediate (re)action, sharing information, protection of team, also risking the loss. If we will be able to define this procedures, put them to overall synergy, then it will not hard to prepare for it and incorporate it into training programs. Also, we can use this experience for building higher level units. Those two statements can be described and saturated for creating standardised operational procedures and doctrines.

Command and control, is crucial function for working with UxS device. Big data and not ability to prioritise data about micro-relief jam communicational canals. C4ISTAR structure has to be robust and resilient. Enemy will focus on C2 centres. The war fight will be about breaching the network, creating a gap and destroying more cells working in network, on all commanding levels, across all domains. This can neutralise UxS devices, so the only working elements will be human again. Probably, facing to opposite UxS.

Picture 2. The network-centric warfare [1]

From organisation culture viewpoint, the personnel have to be cooperative with UxS, using augmented and virtual reality, be plug-in-able to network. On the other hand, after destroying or neutralising UxS, in case of long, sources exhausting war, be able to fight in style of 90's.

Not only people has to evolution mind-set. There is necessary change all the support and maintenance. Only a battery management is huge topic as itself. Next topics can be repairing operational algorhytm, storage of big data etc. This all respecting requirements for agility, mobility, deployment and re-deployment, financial sources and other attributes.

Conclusion

Implementation of UxS has to be based on utilisation of small UxS units, experimentally incorporated into tactical units. It is important to learn, how to operate with them and if it will be possible, deploy them. This this the only way, how to make huge step forward, following technological development. Making UxS usual in military job as soon as possible can open all the relations not only for researches, but also for users, new issues can be fixed together and we can reach wider implementation of UxS.

References:

1. Kott, A., & Stump, E. (Unk.). Intelligent Autonomous Things on the Battlefield. Arxiv.org. Retrieved October 20, 2022, from <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1902/1902.10086.pdf>
2. Kurzweil, R. (2018). Kurzweil Curve. <Http://www.americanprof.net/>. Retrieved September 10, 2022, from <http://www.americanprof.net/apn-ai/index.php/tool-box/ray-kurzweil>
3. STO. (2020). Science & Technology Trends 2020-2040: Exploring the S&T Edge. <Www.nato.int>. Retrieved September 10, 2022, from https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/2020/4/pdf/190422-ST_Tech_Trends_Report_2020-2040.pdf
4. Valášek, T. (2018). New perspectives on shared security: NATO's next 70 years, from https://carnegieendowment.org/files/NATO_int_final1.pdf
5. Zahradníček, P. (2022). Unammned autonomous systems of Army of the Czech Republic in future conflict on land domain: Final thesis of general staff course.